

Synthesis, spectral characterization, thermal decomposition and diuretic study of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes with 4-chloro-*N*-(2-furfuryl)-5-sulfamoyl anthranilic acid

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Abstract : The biological activity of many drugs has been seen to be improved on complexing with metal ions, subsequently promoting their use in pharmacology. The present work deals with the synthesis of metal complexes derived from diuretic drug furosemide and its physico-chemical analysis to find out ligand-metal ratio in solution. Metal complexes of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} have been synthesized with furosemide (FROSM) i.e. 4-chloro-*N*-(2-furfuryl)-5-sulfamoylanthranilic acid. The metal complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance measurements, IR, electronic, Mass, thermal analyses and SEM. Complexes were found to have the general composition, ML₂, M = Co^{II} and Ni^{II}, L₂ = 4-chloro-*N*-(2-furfuryl)-5-sulfamoylanthranilic acid. The mode of bonding and overall geometry of the complexes has been inferred through IR, and electronic spectral studies which suggest that Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complex possess octahedral geometry. The synthesized ligand as well as their metal complexes was screened for diuretic activity.

Keywords : Diuretic, metal complexes, IR, UV-Vis, thermal analysis, SEM.

Introduction

During the past decade, much attention has been given on metal-based therapeutics for treatment of many ailments. Drug inducing states of increased urine flow are called as diuretics. It is known fact that diuretic drugs are used to adjust the volume and composition of body fluid in variety of disorders. These disorders include nephritic syndrome, renal failure, hypertension, cirrhosis and so on¹. 4-Chloro-*N*-(2-furfuryl)-5-sulfamoylanthranilic acid (FROSM) is a potent and widely used diuretic in the treatment of edematous states associated with cardiac, chronic renal failure^{2,3}, hypertension, congestive heart failure^{4,5} and cirrhosis of the liver⁶. Furosemide (FROSM), as we know, is 4-chloro-*N*-(2-furfuryl)-5-sulfamoylanthranilic acid, a potent high ceiling (loop) diuretic, mainly used in the treatment of hypertension. As metals play important roles in biological systems, the literature reveals that the complexes of metallic salts are more potent and less toxic in many a cases as compared to the parent drug². Due to the growing interest in ligands and their transition with metal complexes and considering the importance of drugs and their complexes, it has been considered necessary to

synthesize and characterize some transition metal complexes of respective diuretic drug furosemide with transition metals like Co^{II} and Ni^{II}⁷⁻⁹. Nickel and cobalt also plays important roles in biological systems. In the present research communication, the synthesis and characterization studies of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes with 4-chloro-*N*-(2-furfuryl)-5-sulfamoylanthranilic acid (FROSM) a diuretic drug has been reported. Study has also been carried out on the biological activities of ligand and metal complexes¹⁰. As an ingredient of research, the diuretic activity of furosemide and its metal complexes was utilized on albino rats and results have been found to be encouraging as compared to the parent drug¹¹.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All the chemicals used in this work were of analytical reagent grades. Pure sample of furosemide (FROSM) was received as a gift sample from Lupin, Mandideep. Metal salts (CoCl₂·6H₂O and NiCl₂·6H₂O) were obtained from Sigma Aldrich in high purity.

Techniques :

Elemental analysis (C, H, N) were carried out on Elementar, Vario analyzer. IR spectra ($4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the ligands and metal complexes were recorded using KBr disc on Bruker FT-IR spectrometer. Electronic spectra of the metal complexes in DMF were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer UV Win Lab spectrophotometer. The mass spectra were carried out on the Waters Quadrupole Time of Flight (Q-TOF) Micromass (LC-MS) spectrometer. A simultaneous TG/DSC was recorded on Mettler Toledo model. SEM images were recorded in a Hitachi SEM analyzer.

Synthesis of complexes :

For the synthesis of the complexes, 0.02 mol ligand solution was prepared in 80% methanol-water solvent and thereafter the required metal salt (0.01 mol) was added. The pH of the solution was adjusted in the range of 8 to 9 by adding sodium hydroxide. The resulting solution was refluxed for 4–5 h. The refluxed solutions were kept for some days whereby solid crystalline compounds appeared in the solution, which were filtered, washed with 80% methanol-water mixture, dried and weighed. Melting points of the complexes were also recorded.

Diuretic activity :

The diuretic activity of Ni^{II} complex was checked on Wistar Albino rats of 4 months of both sexes, weighing between 140 to 180 g. The animals were acclimatized to the standard laboratory conditions in cross ventilated animal house at temperature $25 \pm 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, relative humidity 44–56% and light and dark cycles of 12–12 h, fed with standard pallet diet and water *ad libitum* during experiment.

Results and discussion

The ligand and its metal complexes are coloured and stable at room temperature. The ligand is soluble in common organic solvents, but the complexes are found to be soluble in DMSO and DMF. The elemental analyses data concur well with the planned formulae for the ligand and also recognised the ML_2 composition of the metal complexes. Based on elemental analysis and Mass, the composition was assigned to the complexes and presented in Table 1. It has been found that complexes are insoluble in water but fairly soluble in DMSO. It has also been found

that complexes are non-hygroscopic which are stable at room temperature.

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) characterization :

The formation of metal complexes has been confirmed by IR spectroscopy by comparing the IR spectra of metal complexes with that of ligand. IR spectra of FROSM demonstrates that the characteristic absorption bands for stretching vibration of asymmetric amine N–H appeared at 3397.24 cm^{-1} , secondary amine N–H appeared at 3351.07 cm^{-1} , symmetric N–H stretching appeared at 3283.79 cm^{-1} and the peak at 3116.76 cm^{-1} was due to the C–H stretching¹². The peaks at 1671.60 cm^{-1} and 1564.81 cm^{-1} were assigned for C=O asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of carbonyl group $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ and the C–Cl stretching vibration appeared at 582 cm^{-1} respectively¹³. In the $\nu(\text{OH})$ water region the spectra of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes show one sharp band attributed to the presence of coordinated water¹⁴. The IR spectra of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} metal complexes exhibit bands in the range ($3405\text{--}3643\text{ cm}^{-1}$), which were not found in the ligand and indicates the presence of coordinated water molecules. The N–H stretching at 3283 cm^{-1} of the FROSM was shifted in the spectra of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} metal complexes; thus the secondary amine group is coordinated. The almost identical absorption bands were obtained from FROSM- Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes¹¹. Thus, the IR study indicates that the metal ions of FROSM behave as bidentate in the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes with stable.

Electronic spectra :

The spectra of the FROSM- Co^{II} complex contain absorption bands in the range $18228\text{--}19607\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $22507\text{--}25724\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions in a distorted octahedral configuration. The FROSM- Co^{II} complex has a magnetic moment of 4.79 B.M. which is an agreement with the reported value for octahedral Co^{II} complex. The molar ratio between both the metal complexes and the drug was determined using the continuous variation method¹⁵. It was found that the ratio between nickel, cobalt and drug is 1 : 2. In general the electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complex showed an intense peak at $25411\text{--}33444\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The doublet structure of the ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition in the spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex is indicative of a

Table 1. Elemental analysis data and some physical properties of FROSM and its metal complexes

Sr. no.	Empirical formula of Ligand/Complex	Molecular weight (g/mol)	Colour	m.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
					C	H	N	Metal
1.	[(L) ₂]	330.745	White to light yellow	223.64	42.28 (43.63)	3.32 (3.35)	8.15 (8.48)	-
2.	[Co(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	755.51	Pale pink	330.35	37.27 (38.15)	2.49 (2.93)	6.73 (7.41)	6.87 (7.80)
3.	[Ni(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	755.27	Light green	340.42	36.57 (38.16)	2.66 (2.94)	6.35 (7.42)	6.59 (7.77)

trans tetragonally distorted octahedral structure. The Ni^{II} complex reported herein has a room temperature magnetic moment value of 3.24 B.M., which is within the normal range observed for octahedral Ni^{II} complex¹¹. The absorption data for the complexes are given in Table 2.

revealed that the degradation occurred in multiple stages, following a complex mechanism. Thermal behaviour of all complexes can be explained as follows :

- The TG curve follows the decrease in sample mass with increase in temperature.

Table 2. Electronic spectral data and magnetic moments values of the ligand and its complexes

Sr. No.	Ligand/Complexes	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Wavelength (cm ⁻¹)	Band assignments	Suggested geometry
1.	[Co(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	4.79	18228–19607 22507–25724	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ A _{2g} (F) ⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)	Octahedral
2.	[Ni(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	3.24	25411–33444	³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (P)	Octahedral

Mass spectral analysis :

The mass spectrum of [Ni(C₁₂H₁₁ClN₂O₅S)₂(H₂O)₂] shows a molecular ion peak (m⁺) at m/z 757 (I) is due to [Ni(L)₂(H₂O)₂]⁺ which suggest the monomeric nature^{16,17} of the complex and confirms the proposed formula¹⁸. Other peaks of appreciable intensity observed at m/z values 721 is due the loss of 2H₂O from m⁺ ion (I), at 685 is due to the loss of Cl⁺ from (I), at 475 (II) is due to the loss of C₇H₅O₄N₂ClS⁺ from (I), at 431 is due to the loss of CO₂ from (II), at 397 (III) is due to the loss of C₄H₄O from (II), at 371 is due to the loss of C₂H₂ from (III), at 331 is due to the loss of metal from (III), at 248 is due to C₇H₅O₄N₂ClS⁺ and peak at 202 is due to the loss of CO₂ from C₇H₅O₄N₂ClS⁺. A mass spectrum of the Ni^{II}-FROSM complex is in good agreement with the calculated values. The relative intensities of these peaks give an idea of the stabilities of the various fragments.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

Thermal analyses of drug FROSM and its complexes were carried out by the TG-DSC technique in the temperature range 50–800 °C with a sample heating rate 10 °C/min in nitrogen atmosphere. The experimental results

- The DSC plot of FROSM drug shows a sharp endothermic peak near 210–220.8 °C corresponding to its melting temperature¹⁵.

In the thermal decompositions of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes the weight-loss step between 100–300 °C may correspond the elimination of coordinated water molecules. The weight-loss step between 350–500 °C may be attributed to the loss of organic moiety of the complex molecule. The final decomposition continues up to 800 °C and on further increasing the temperature no weight loss was observed which may be attributed to formation of stable metal oxide^{2,12,13}.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) :

The surface morphology of compound was studied using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Pure FROSM has been characterized by the presence of crystalline particle of regular size and appeared as crystalline particles without a definite shape. SEM of pure drug, confirmed the crystalline character of furosemide and the amorphous character of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes. Crystals of FROSM mixed with Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes were seen adhering to their surfaces. The photomicrograph of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} metal complexes show small size particles with

Fig. 1. Scanning Electronic Micrograph of (a) FROSM, (b) FROSM-Co^{II} and Ni^{II} metal complexes.

the tendency to aggregation, suggesting the existence of an amorphous product with the presence of a single component in the complex. This indicates a maximum or complete complex formation and the drug was also found uniformly dispersed at the molecular level in the microspheres as observed by SEM analysis¹⁹. The scanning electron micrographs of the pure drug FROSM and its metal complexes are shown in Fig. 1.

Diuretic activity :

The results of diuretic activity are shown in Table 3. The diuretic activities of Ni^{II} complex of FROSM were significant ($p < 0.01$) when as compared to control²⁰⁻²². The values are expressed as mean \pm SEM ($n = 6$), compared with control (ANOVA followed by Dunnett's t -test), $**p < 0.01$. Statistical significance on comparison with standard drug and control groups p values less than 0.05 were considered as significant. The results confirm that nickel and copper complexes of FROSM show better activity than the parent drug.

Conclusion

Based on the physico-chemical and spectral aspects as discussed above it is implicit that the complexes suggested as octa coordinated may probably having octahedral geometry. Thermal study revealed that simultaneous presence of crystal and coordinated water and complexes are

thermally stable. The diuretic study results have been found to be encouraging with metal complexes as compared to the parent drug. The results obtained by different characterization techniques clearly indicate that the complexation of FROSM with Co^{II} and Ni^{II} ions will lead to a better therapeutic efficacy. Based on the above studies, following structure may be assigned to the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of FROSM :

Fig. 2. The structure of FROSM.

Fig. 3. The proposed structure of the complexes : M = Co^{II} and Ni^{II}.

Table 3. Effect of complex on urine volume and electrolyte contents of urine at 24 h

Sr. no.	Treatment	Dose (mg/kg)	Urine volume (ml)	Electrolyte concentration in PPM		
				Na ⁺	K ⁺	Cl ⁻
1.	Control (vehicle)	1 ml/100 g	2.0 \pm 0.35	86 \pm 4	64.4 \pm 3	110 \pm 5
2.	FROSM	10	5.4 \pm 0.32**	131.5 \pm 6**	119.4 \pm 3**	141.3 \pm 6**
3.	FROSM-Ni ^{II}	10	5.5 \pm 0.36**	133.8 \pm 7**	111 \pm 3**	145.6 \pm 3**

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